

GSM Based Automated Embedded System for Monitoring and Controlling of Smart Grid

Authors : Amit Sachan

Abstract : The purpose of this paper is to acquire the remote electrical parameters like Voltage, Current and Frequency from Smart grid and send these real time values over GSM network using GSM Modem/phone along with temperature at power station. This project is also designed to protect the electrical circuitry by operating an Electromagnetic Relay. The Relay can be used to operate a Circuit Breaker to switch off the main electrical supply. User can send commands in the form of SMS messages to read the remote electrical parameters. This system also can automatically send the real time electrical parameters periodically (based on time settings) in the form of SMS. This system also send SMS alerts whenever the Circuit Breaker trips or whenever the Voltage or Current exceeds the predefined limits.

Keywords : GSM Modem, Initialization of ADC module of microcontroller, PIC-C compiler for Embedded C programming, PIC kit 2 programmer for dumping code into Micro controller, Express SCH for Circuit design, Proteus for hardware simulation.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014